

Pregnancy with Osteogenesis Imperfecta - Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Osteogenesis imperfecta is a rare inherited Connective tissue disorder with an expression that varies from mild to severe disease affecting bone, Sclera and middle ear. Fertility is preserved, especially in those patients with type I. We present hereby a pregnant woman with Osteogenesis imperfecta that was managed with multi disciplinary approach till postpartum duration. The objective of this report is to determine maternal and neonatal complications and prenatal diagnosis.

KEY WORDS: pregnancy, brittle bone disease, osteogenesis imperfecta, materna outcome, fetal outcome

INTRODUCTION:

Osteogenesis Imperfecta (OI), brittle bone disease characterised by multiple bone fractures, is a rare connective tissue disorder with variable phenotypic presentation.^[1] It occurs due to deficiencies in the synthesis of type I collagen. It has an incidence of 1/10,000 in the general population, and 1/25,000 to 30,000 in obstetric patients.^[2] It results from mutations in COL1A1 and COL1A2 genes which codes for collagen, involved in endochondral ossification, with consequent bone fragility and multiple spontaneous fractures or after mild traumas.^[3]

Though rare, it is the most common inherited disorder of connective tissue. There are nine major phenotypically different subtypes, which vary widely in severity. Type I (also known as classic non-deforming osteogenesis imperfecta with blue sclerae) is the most common with mild involvement without major deformities, and normal stature. Type II (also known as prenatally lethal Osteogenesis Imperfecta) is the most severe affecting neonates, and it is usually incompatible with life. In type III (progressively

deforming osteogenesis imperfecta) patients have short stature, triangular faces, and bone deformities. Type IV with hypertrophic calluses and calcification of the interosseous membrane of the forearm.^[4]

Pregnancy in osteogenesis imperfecta poses a major life-threatening risk to both mother and child. Venous thromboembolism, impaired wound healing, PPH, cardiac abnormalities and fetal congenital heart disease commonly complicate such pregnancy. Also with autosomal dominant inheritance, there may be 50% chance of fetal affection.

CASE REPORT:

A 33 years, **G2 P1 L1** with previous LSCS with Rh- negative pregnancy with known case of epilepsy with Osteogenesis Imperfecta (type 1) reported to ANC OPD at 24 weeks of gestation for routine ANC checkup.

Her first child had multiple fractures during his initial years of life and had blue sclera (Figure 1) which on screening was diagnosed as due to OI. Subsequent parental screening confirmed OI. She was also on antiepileptic drugs since 6 years.

Patient received initial antenatal care at other private clinic where she was offered invasive prenatal screening but the couple refused and opted for continuation of pregnancy.

Though her dual marker, NT/NB and target scan (Figure 2) were all normal. She was receiving antiepileptic drugs along with thyroid supplementation. Beside routine antenatal care, she

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Figure 1: Showing blue sclera of the patient.

Figure 2: Prenatal ultrasound showing mildly curved lower limbs.

received antenatal prophylaxis and vigilant fetomaternal monitoring. She was put on calcium and vit D supplementation. At 32 weeks however her liquor started reducing, for which she was managed conservatively and was delivered by Cesarean section at 37 completed weeks under GA, as patient also had cervical disc prolapse.

DISCUSSION:

Fertility is preserved especially in patients with OI type I^[6] and pregnancy can be carried to term. The fetal diagnosis can be done through chorionic villus sampling and imaging exams of the fetus. If fetal OI is confirmed pre-natally, especially the lethal type, cesarean section is not indicated because, besides increasing maternal morbidity, it does not improve fetal prognosis. Cesarean sections do not decrease the number of fetal fractures in newborns with non lethal types of OI.

With advancement in medical care more women affected by connective tissue disorders are surviving through reproductive years and becoming pregnant. However, pregnancies can be carried to term with close antenatal surveillance and multidisciplinary team approach forms the mainstay of managing such pregnancies.

CONCLUSION:

Preconception counseling should be offered to those patients planning a pregnancy or to those who desire effective contraception, including sterilization for those who choose not to have a pregnancy or after a pregnancy.

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